

Supplementary information 1: Statistical distribution of the mean distance between each anemone occupied by a self-recruit and the other anemones (A) and the distance between self-recruits and their parents (B) at Kimbe island. Red dotted lines represent the mean of each statistical distribution (A: $388\text{m} \pm 37\text{m}$; B: $254\text{m} \pm 189\text{m}$). Based on a Wilcoxon test, these two statistical distributions were significantly different ($P < 0.001$). Note that 47% of self-recruits were located at less than 200m from their parents.

